

NOUNS: DEFINITION, TYPES WITH EXAMPLES

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Abstract: In this article, the subject of Noun is detailed information about the types and types of nouns. You will also learn more about nouns.

Keywords: noun, verb, complement, ideas, speech, subject, function, perform, indirect, proper noun, common noun.

INTRODUCTION.

What Is a Noun?

Nouns are a part of speech that comprise words that are used to name people, places, animals, objects and ideas. Almost every sentence will definitely have a noun, and they perform different roles in a sentence. Nouns can act as the subject, an indirect object, a direct object, a subject complement and an object complement. Nouns can also function as adjectives and verbs.

Examples of Nouns:

People – Rahul, Sheela, Man, Person, Tommy, Women, Girl, The Prime Minister

Places – Bangalore, India, Mexico, North Pole, South Africa, The Nile River,
Classroom, Bedroom, Basketball Court, Cricket Ground, Swimming Pool

Animals/Birds/Aquatic Animals/Reptiles

Lion, Zebra, Snake, Ostrich, Flamingo, Bear, Cat, Fish, Shark

Ideas – Evolution, Invention, Extinction, Argument, Destruction

Objects/Things – Bat, Cycle, Curtains, Paper, Bag, Blackboard, Cupboard

THE MAIN PART.

Types of Nouns

Nouns can be broadly classified into:

1. Proper Nouns: Nouns that are used to name a person, place or thing specifically are called a proper noun. Proper nouns always begin with a capital letter.

Examples:

My name is Rose. (Name of a particular person)

This is my dog, Bruno. (Name of a specific pet animal owned by someone)

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2. Common nouns are those nouns that refer to a generic item, group or place. This means that, unlike proper nouns, they are not used to identify specific people, places or objects. Common nouns are not capitalised unless they appear at the beginning of a sentence.

I bought a pen yesterday. (Common object)

I am going to school. (Common place)

Only ten employees showed up to work today. (Common group)

3. Singular nouns: These are words that are used to name a single person, place, animal, bird or object.

Examples:

There is a little boy in front of our house. (Single person)

That is my daughter. (Single person)

4. Plural nouns refer to a number of people, places, animals or things. Nouns are made plural by adding an ‘s’ or ‘es’ or ‘ies’ or ‘ves’ to the existing root word. Nouns that end with an ‘s’ remain the same. Some nouns remain the same in both their singular and plural forms, and some others have totally different spelling.

Examples:

I need some apples.

Did you find the boxes you were looking for?

I bought mangoes from the market.

5. Countable nouns are those nouns that can be counted or measured.

Examples:

Tom brought ten packets of lays for the trip. (specific number – ten)

6. Uncountable nouns are those nouns that cannot be counted. This category of nouns includes both concrete and abstract nouns.

Examples:

I have a lot of homework to do. (Not specific)

7. Collective Nouns: A collective noun is a naming word that is used to denote a group of objects, animals or people.

Examples:

Collective nouns for groups of animals

A pride of lions

A flock of sheep

A swarm of bees

A herd of elephants

8. Concrete Nouns: A concrete noun refers to objects that are material and can be perceived by the human senses.

Examples:

The book is on the table.

I had a cup of coffee.

Sharon opened the windows.

9. Abstract Nouns: Any entity that cannot be perceived by the five senses of the human body are called an abstract noun.

Examples:

Love is a strong emotion.

Honesty is the best policy.

It takes a lot of courage to raise your voice and stand up against injustice.

You should not misuse the freedom you are given.

Nouns Used as Different Components of a Sentence

Nouns Used as a Subject

When used as a subject, a noun mostly appears at the beginning of a sentence. It can be identified by asking the question ‘who’.

Bruno went to the playground.

The teacher asked the students to submit their assignments.

The elephant was rescued safely after ten long hours.

Categories of Nouns

There are several categories of nouns, and there can be an overlap across the categories. For example, there are common and proper nouns, and concrete and abstract nouns, yet some nouns are both concrete and common, or concrete and proper. It will become clear as you read on. Common nouns are the words that refer to most general things: country, evening, laughter, puppy, umbrella. Common noun examples in the following sentences are in bold for easy identification.

Cathy loves the weekends in the country.

We enjoy swimming after breakfast.

The cup fell and broke.

CONCLUSION.

Proper nouns are the name that identifies someone or something, a person or a place. Proper nouns are capitalized. John is a proper noun, since the word John represents a particular, single example of a thing, John. Proper noun examples: Mary, Jimmy, Aunt Audrey, Honda, Philadelphia Proper noun examples in the following sentences are in bold for easy identification.

Emily loved spending time with her Aunt Nancy in Paris.

Buick and Jeep are two important carmakers.

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